

On (Fuzzy) AT-ideals of AT-algebra

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to introduce and study new algebraic structure, called AT-algebra and investigate some of its properties. We give the notion of AT-ideal of AT-algebra and quotient AT-Algebras, several theorems, properties are stated and proved. We introduce the notion of fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra, several theorems, properties are stated and proved. The fuzzy relations on AT-algebras are also studied as isomorphic and normal.

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AT-algebra, AT-subalgebra, AT-ideal, homomorphism of AT-ideal on AT-algebra, quotient AT-Algebras, fuzzy AT-subalgebra, fuzzy AT-ideal, homomorphisms of fuzzy AT-ideal on AT-algebras, image and pre-image of fuzzy AT-ideals, normal fuzzy AT-ideal.

1.Introduction

Y. Imai and K. Iseki introduced two classes of abstract algebras: BCK-algebras and BCI-algebras([7],[8],[9]). It is known that the class of BCK-algebras is a proper subclass of the class of BCI-algebras. The class of all BCH-algebras is a quasivariety. Q.p. Hu and X. Li in ([5],[6]), posed an interesting problem whether the class of BCK-algebras is a variety. In([1],[2]), S. Asawasamrit introduced KK-algebras which is a generalization of BCK / BCI-algebras and obtained several results. S.M. Mostafa et al. ([4],[10]) introduced a new algebraic structure which is called KUS-algebras and investigated some related properties.

In this paper , we introduce new of abstract algebras: is called AT-algebras and define its subalgebras and ideals .We study homomorphism of AT-algebra and describe its properties. We consider the fuzzification of AT-ideals on AT-algebras, and investigate related properties. We investigate how to deal with the homomorphic and inverse image of fuzzy AT-ideals on AT-algebras. We give isomorphism of AT-ideal and fuzzy AT-ideals on AT-algebras. We give definition and some basic preliminaries of normal fuzzy AT-ideals on AT-algebras.

2.Preliminaries

In this section, certain definitions, Known results and examples that will be used in the sequel are described.

Definition2.1.([5],[7],[8]). A **BCI-algebra** is a nonempty set X with a constant (0) and a binary operation $(*)$ satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$.

- (a) $((x*y)*(x*z))*(z*y)=0,$
- (b) $(x*(x*y))*y=0,$
- (c) $x*x=0,$
- (d) $x*y=y*x=0$ implies $x=y,$
- (e) $0*x=0$ implies $x=0$,, where $x \leq y$ is defined by $x*y=0$.

If(f) $x*0=0$, then the BCI-algebra is called a **BCK-algebra**. It is shown that every BCK-algebra is a BCI-algebra but not conversely .

If $(X ; *, 0)$ is an algebra of type $(2,0)$ satisfying (c) , (d) and (g) $(x*y)*z=(x*z)*y$, then X is called a BCH-algebra. It is shown that every BCI-algebra is a BCH-algebra but not conversely.

New, we introduce the concept of AT-algebra and give several characteristics.

Definition2.2. An **AT-algebra** is a nonempty set X with a constant (0) and a binary operation $(*)$ satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i) $(x*y)*((y*z)*(x*z))=0$,
- (ii) $0*x=x$,
- (iii) $x*0=0$.

In what follows, let $(X ; *, 0)$ denote an AT-algebra unless otherwise specified .

For brevity we also call X an AT-algebra. In X we can define a binary relation (\leq) by : $x \leq y$ if and only if , $y * x = 0$.

Remark 2.3. $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra if and only if, it satisfies that: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (i') : $(y * z) * (x * z) \leq x * y$,
- (ii') : $x \leq y$ if and only if, $y * x = 0$..

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	1	0	3	3
3	0	0	2	0	2
4	0	0	0	0	0

It is easy to show that $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra.

Proposition 2.5. In any AT-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- 1) $z * z = 0$,
- 2) $z*(x * z) = 0$,
- 3) $y * ((y * z) * z) = 0$,
- 4) $x * y = 0$ implies that $x * 0 = y * 0$,
- 5) $0*x=0*y$ implies that $x=y$.

Proof.

- 1) Put $x = y = 0$ in (i), we get $(0*0) * ((0* z)*(0*z)) = 0$, and by (ii) follows that $z * z = 0$.
- 2) Put $y = 0$ in (i), $(x*0) * ((0* z)*(x*z)) = 0$, implies that $(0*z)*(x*z) = 0$, and by (ii) follows that $z *(x * z) = 0$.
- 3) Put $x = 0$ in (i), we get $(0*y) * ((y* z) *(0*z)) = 0$, and by (ii) follows That $y*((y * z)* z) = 0$.
- 4) It is clear.
- 5) It is clear . \triangle

Proposition 2.6. In any AT-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- a) $x \leq y$ implies that $y * z \leq x * z$,
- b) $x \leq y$ implies that $z * x \leq z * y$
- c) $z * x \leq z * y$ implies that $x \leq y$ (left cancellation law).

Proof.

- a) Since by (i), $(y * x) * ((x * z) * (y * z)) = 0$, but $x \leq y$ implies $(y * x) = 0$, then $0 * ((x * z) * (y * z)) = 0$. By (ii), we get $(x * z) * (y * z) = 0$, i.e; $y * z \leq x * z$.
- b) Since $x \leq y$ implies $(y * x) = 0$, by (i), we obtain $(z * y) * ((y * x) * (z * x)) = 0$, but $(y * x) = 0$, then $(z * y) * (0 * (z * x)) = 0$. By (ii), we get $(z * y) * (z * x) = 0$, i.e; $z * x \leq z * y$
- c) $x = 0 * x = (z * z) * x = z * (z * x) \leq z * (z * y) = (z * z) * y = 0 * y = y$
 \triangle

Proposition 2.7. In any AT-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- a) $x = 0 * (0 * x)$,
- b) $x * y \leq z$ imply $z * y \leq x$.

Proof.

a) $0 * x = 0 * (0 * x) = (0 * 0) * (0 * x) = 0 * (0 * (0 * x))$, then by proposition (2.5(5)),
 $x = 0 * (0 * x)$.

b) We know that $x * y \leq z$ imply $z * (x * y) = 0$, but $x * (y * z) =$
 $y * (x * z)$ by (a), we obtain $x * (z * y) = 0$, i.e; $z * y \leq x$. \triangle

Example 2.8. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	1	0	2	4
3	0	0	3	0	2
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra.

Remark 2.9. In this paper, we will denote N for the set of all nonnegative integers, i.e., $0, 1, 2, \dots$, and N^* for the set of all natural numbers, i.e., $1, 2, 3, \dots$, and we will also use the following notation in brevity:

$y^0 * x = x$, $y^n * x = y * (y * (\dots * (y * x)))$, (n times), where x, y are any elements in an AT-algebra and $n \in N^*$.

Proposition 2.10. Let x, y be any element in AT-algebra X . Then: for any $n \in N$,

- 1) $((y * x) * x)^n * x = y^n * x$,
- 2) $(x^n * 0) * 0 = (x * 0)^n * 0$.

Proof.

1) Proceed by induction on (n) and defined the statement $P(n)$,

$((y * x) * x)^n * x = y^n * x$. We see that $P(0)$ is true, $((y * x) * x)^0 * x = x = y^0 * x$.

Assume that $P(k)$ is true for some arbitrary $k \geq 0$, that is $((y * x) * x)^k * x = y^k * x$.

Since $((y * x) * x)^{k+1} * x = ((y * x) * x) * (((y * x) * x)^k * x)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= ((y * x) * x) * (y^k * x) = y^k * (((y * x) * x) * x) \\
 &= y^k * (y * x) = y^{k+1} * x.
 \end{aligned}$$

This show that $P(k+1)$ is true by the principle of mathematical induction , $P(n)$ is true for each $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 2) \quad & \text{Since } (x^{n*} 0)^* 0 = (x^*(x^{n-1} * 0))^* 0 \\
 & = (x^*0)^*((x^{n-1} * 0)^* 0) \\
 & = (x^*0)^*((x^*(x^{n-2} * 0))^* 0) \\
 & = (x^*0)^* ((x^*0)^* ((x^{n-2} * 0)^* 0)) \\
 & = (x^*0)^{2*}((x^{n-2} * 0)^* 0) = \dots = (x^*0)^n * 0. \triangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 2.11. Let x be any element in AT-algebra X . Then $((x^*0)^* 0)^*x$ is a positive element of X for every $x \in X$, where $(x$ is a positive element of X if $x \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow x^*0=0)$.

Proof. Since $((x^*0)^* 0)^*x = (((x^*0)^* 0)^*0) * (x^*0) = (x^*0)^*(x^*0) = 0$. Therefore, $((x^*0)^* 0)^*x$ is a positive element of X . \triangle

Definition 2.12. A nonempty subset S of an AT-algebra X is called an **AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X** if $x*y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 2.13. A nonempty subset I of an AT-algebra X is called an **AT-ideal of AT-algebra X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$

AT₁) $0 \in I$;

AT₂) $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x*z \in I$.

Example 2.14.

(a) Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d, e\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	a	b	c	d	e
0	0	a	b	c	d	e
a	0	0	b	b	d	e
b	0	0	0	a	d	e
c	0	0	0	0	d	e
d	0	0	0	a	0	e
e	0	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, a\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ are AT-ideals of X .

(b) Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	3
2	0	0	0	3
3	0	0	0	0

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, 3\}$ are AT-ideals of X .

Proposition 2.15. Every AT-ideal of AT-algebra X is an AT-subalgebra.

Proof.

Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , for all $x, y \in X$ and let $x, y \in I$, then $x * (0 * y) \in I$ and $0 \in I$. Hence by (ii), $x * y \in I$. Therefore I is an AT-subalgebra. \triangle

Proposition 2.16. If I is an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X and J is an AT-ideal of I , then J is an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Since J is an AT-ideal of I , then $0 \in J$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ such that $x * (y * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$. By assumption, I is an AT-ideal of X , so $x * z \in I$ and $y \in J$. From J is an AT-ideal of I , so $x * z \in J$. Therefore, J is an AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Theorem 2.17. Let $\{J_i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a family of AT-ideals of AT-algebra X where $J_n \subseteq J_{n+1}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Let $\{J_i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a family of AT-ideals of X . It can be proved easily that $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n \subseteq X$. Since J_i is an AT-ideal of X for all i , so $0 \in \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$. Let $(x * (y * z)) \in \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ and $y \in \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$. It follows that $(x * (y * z)) \in J_j$ for some $j \in \mathbb{N}$ and $y \in J_k$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Furthermore, let $J_j \subseteq J_k$. Hence $(x * (y * z)) \in J_k$ and $y \in J_k$. By assumption, J_k is an AT-ideal of X , it follows that $x * z \in J_k$. Therefore, $x * z \in \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$, proving that $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Theorem 2.18. Let $\{J_i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a family of AT-subalgebras of an AT-algebra X where $J_n \subseteq J_{n+1}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-subalgebras of X .

Proof.

Let $\{J_i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a family of AT-subalgebras of X . By proposition (2.15) and theorem (2.21), $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-ideal of X . We will show that $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-subalgebra of X .

Let $x, y \in \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$. It follows that $x \in J_j$ for some $j \in \mathbb{N}$ and $y \in J_k$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$. We assume that $j \leq k$, we obtain $J_j \subseteq J_k$. That is, $x \in J_k$ and $x \in J_k$. Since J_k is an AT-subalgebra of X , we get $x * y \in J_k \subseteq \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$. This proves that $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} J_n$ is an AT-subalgebra of X . \triangle

Theorem 2.19. Let $\{I_j : j \in J\}$ be a family of AT-ideals of an AT-algebra X . Then $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ is an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Let $\{I_j : j \in J\}$ be a family of AT-ideals of X . It is obvious that $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j \subseteq X$. Since $0 \in I_j$, for all $j \in J$, it follows that $0 \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$. Let $x * (y * z) \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ and $y \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$. We get that $x * (y * z) \in I_j$ and $y \in I_j$, for all $j \in J$, then $x * z \in I_j$, for all $j \in J$. Because I_j is an AT-ideal of X . So $x * z \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$, proving our theorem. \triangle

Theorem 2.20. Let $\{I_j : j \in J\}$ be a family of AT-subalgebras of an AT-algebra X . Then $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ is an AT-subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Let $\{I_j : j \in J\}$ be a family of AT-subalgebras of X . By proposition (2.15) and theorem (2.23), $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ is an AT-ideal of X . We will show that $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ is an AT-subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$. It follows that $x, y \in I_j$, for all $j \in J$. Since I_j is an AT-subalgebra of X and $x * y \in I_j$, for all $j \in J$, then $x * y \in \bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$. This show that $\bigcap_{j \in J} I_j$ is an AT-subalgebra of X . \triangle

3. Quotient AT-Algebras

In this section, we describe congruence on AT-algebras.

Definition 3.1. Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . Define a **relation** (\sim) on X by: $x \sim y$ if and only if, $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$, as define a relation (\sim) in [3].

Theorem 3.2. If I is an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , then the relation (\sim) is an equivalence relation on X .

Proof.

Let I be an AT-ideal of X and $x, y, z \in X$. By proposition (2.5(1)), $x * x = 0$ and assumption, $x * x \in I$. That is, $x \sim x$. Hence (\sim) is reflexive.

Next, suppose that $x \sim y$. It follows that $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$. Then $y \sim x$, so (\sim) is symmetric.

Finally, let $x \sim y$ and $y \sim z$. Then $x * y, y * x, y * z, z * y \in I$ and $(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 0 \in I$. It follows that $(y * z) * (x * z) \in I$, and since $y * z \in I$, so $x * z \in I$. Similarly, $z * x \in I$. Thus (\sim) is transitive. Therefore (\sim) is an equivalence relation. \triangle

Lemma 3.3. Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . For any $x, y, u, v \in X$, if $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, then $u * x \sim v * y$.

Proof.

Assume that $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, for any $x, y, u, v \in X$, then $u * v, v * u, x * y, y * x \in I$ and by (i), we see that $(u * v) * ((v * x) * (u * x)) = 0$ and $(v * u) * ((u * x) * (v * x)) = 0$.

From assumption and I is an ideal of X , these imply that $(v * x) * (u * x) \in I$ and $(u * x) * (v * x) \in I$. This shows that $u * x \sim v * x \dots (1)$.

On the other hand, by theorem(2.5), we have that $(x * y) * ((y * v) * (x * v)) = 0$ and $(y * x) * ((x * v) * (y * v)) = 0$. From assumption and I is an AT-ideal of X , these imply that $(y * v) * (x * v) \in I$ and $(x * v) * (y * v) \in I$. Thus $v * x \sim v * y \dots (2)$.

From (1) and (2), $u * x \sim v * y$. This completes the proof. \triangle

Corollary 3.4. If I is an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , then the relation (\sim) is a congruence relation on X .

Proof.

By theorem (3.2) and lemma (3.3). \triangle

Definition 3.5. Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . Given $x \in X$, the **equivalence class** $[x]_I$ of x is defined as the set of all element of X that are equivalent to x , that is, $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$.

We define the **set** $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$ and a **binary operation** (\circ) on X/I by $[x]_I \circ [y]_I = [x * y]_I$.

Theorem 3.6. If I is an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X with $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, then the binary operation \circ is a mapping from $X/I \times X/I$ to X/I .

Proof.

Let $[x_1]_I, [x_2]_I, [y_1]_I, [y_2]_I \in X/I$ such that $[x_1]_I = [x_2]_I$ and $[y_1]_I = [y_2]_I$. It follows that $x_1 \sim x_2$ and $y_1 \sim y_2$. By lemma (3.3), $x_1 * y_1 \sim x_2 * y_2$, proving that $[x_1 * y_1]_I = [x_2 * y_2]_I$. \square

Theorem 3.7. If I is an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , then $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an AT-algebra. Moreover, the set X/I is called **the quotient AT-algebra**.

Proof.

Let $[x]_I, [y]_I, [z]_I \in X/I$. Then

$$([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ (([y]_I \circ [z]_I) \circ ([x]_I \circ [z]_I)) = [x * y]_I \circ ([y * z]_I \circ [x * z]_I) \\ = [x * y]_I \circ [(y * z) * (x * z)]_I = [(x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z))]_I = [0]_I.$$

It is clear that $[0]_I \circ [x]_I = [0 * x]_I = [x]_I$ and $[x]_I \circ [0]_I = [x * 0]_I = [0]_I$.

Therefore, $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an AT-algebra. \square

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	3
2	0	0	0	3
3	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an AT-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 2\}$ is an AT-ideal of X . We can get that $X/I = \{[0]_I, [2]_I\}$, where $[0]_I = [1]_I = \{0, 1\}$ and $[2]_I = [3]_I = \{2, 3\}$. Let (\circ) be defined on X/I by:

\circ	$[0]_I$	$[2]_I$
$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$	$[2]_I$
$[2]_I$	$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$

Then $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an AT-algebra.

Proposition 3.9. Let X be an AT-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose that I is an AT-ideal of X , then J is an AT-ideal of X if and only if J/I is an AT-ideal of X/I .

Proof.

Let I be an AT-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose firstly that J is an AT-ideal of X , then $J/I = \{[x]_I : x \in J\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in J : x \sim y\}$, and $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$. Obviously, $J/I \subseteq X/I$ and $[0]_I \in J/I$.

Now, let $[x]_I \circ ([y]_I \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$ and $[y]_I \in J/I$.

Then $[x * (y * z)]_I = [x]_I \circ ([y]_I \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$, it follows that $x * (y * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. By assumption, $(x * z) \in J$. Accordingly, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \circ [z]_I \in J/I$, this shows that J/I is an AT-ideal of X/I .

On the other hand, suppose that J/I is an AT-ideal of X/I and I is an AT-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Thus, $0 \in J$. Let $x * (y * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that $[x * (y * z)]_I, [y]_I \in J/I$. Since $[x * (y * z)]_I = [x]_I \circ ([y]_I \circ [z]_I)$, so $[x]_I \circ ([y]_I \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$. By hypothesis, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \circ [z]_I \in J/I$ implies $x * z \in J$. \triangle

Corollary 3.10. Let X be an AT-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose that I is an AT-subalgebra of X . Then J is an AT-subalgebra of X if and only if J/I is an AT-subalgebra of X/I .

Proof.

Similar to that of proposition (3.9). \triangle

Corollary 3.11. Let I, J be two AT-ideals of AT-algebra X with $I \subseteq J$, then I is an AT-ideal of X .

Next, the basic properties of equivalence classes are considered as the following theorem.

Theorem 3.12. Let I be an AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X and $a, b \in X$. Then:

- (1) $[a]_I = I \Leftrightarrow a \in I$,
- (2) $[a]_I = [b]_I$ or $[a]_I \cap [b]_I = \emptyset$.

Proof.

Let I be an AT-subalgebra of X and $a, b \in X$.

- (1) It is clear due to the fact that $a \sim a$ for all $a \in X$ and $a * a = 0 \in I$, so we get that $a \in [a]_I = I$. Conversely, let $x \in [a]_I$. Then $x \sim a$, it follows that

$x * a, a * x \in I$. By hypothesis, $x \in I$. Hence, $[a]_I \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq [a]_I$, choose $x \in I$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of X , we have $x * a, a * x \in I$. Thus, $x \sim a$, this means that $x \in [a]_I$ and shows that $I \subseteq [a]_I$. Consequently, $[a]_I = I$.

(2) Assume that $[a]_I \cap [b]_I \neq \emptyset$. Then there is $x \in [a]_I \cap [b]_I$ such that $x \in [a]_I$ and $x \in [b]_I$. It follows that $x \sim a$ and $x \sim b$, so $a \sim b$ by the symmetric and transitive properties. Thus $[a]_I = [b]_I$. \triangle

4. Homomorphism of AT-algebra

In this section, we introduce the concept AT-homomorphism and we can describe properties of AT-homomorphism of AT-algebra X , also we give examples and results of it.

Definition 4.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be AT-algebras. An **AT-homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ satisfying $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

For example, the zero mapping $g: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ where $g(x) = 0'$, for any $x \in X$, then g is an AT-algebra. In general an AT-homomorphism $f: X \rightarrow Y$ may not be surjective or injective. An injective AT-homomorphism is called monomorphism, a surjective AT-homomorphism is called epimorphism and a bijective AT-homomorphism is called isomorphism. Moreover, we say X is isomorphic to Y , symbolically, $X \cong Y$. The Kernel of the AT-homomorphism f , denoted by $\text{Ker}f$, is the set of elements of X that map to $(0')$ in Y .

Definition 4.2. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping of an AT-algebra X into an AT-algebra Y , and let $I \subseteq X$ and $A \subseteq Y$. **The image of I of X under f** is $f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of A of Y** is $f^{-1}(A) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in A\}$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0'\}$ is called **the Kernel of f** denoted by $\text{Ker}f$.

Next, the basic properties of AT-homomorphism are considered as the following theorem.

Theorem 4.3. Let $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a mapping of an algebra X into an AT-algebra Y . Then: AT-

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If (0) is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .
- (3) $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Proof.

Assume that $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is an AT-homomorphism.

- (1) Since $0 * 0 = 0$, then $f(0) = f(0 * 0) = f(0) * f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) Assume that (0) is the identity in X and $(0')$ is the identity in Y . From (ii), $0' * f(0) = f(0) = 0'$ and

$$f(0) * 0' = f(0) * (f(0) * f(0)) = f(0) * f(0 * 0) = f(0) * f(0) = 0'$$

By (1), we get that $f(0) = 0'$. This show that $f(0')$ is the identity in Y .

- (3) Let $x \leq y$. It follows that $y * x = 0$. So, (1) implies $f(y) * f(x) = f(y * x) = f(0) = 0'$. Hence $f(x) \leq f(y)$. \triangle

Theorem 4.4. Let $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be an AT-homomorphism. Then:

- (1) If I is an AT-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an AT-ideal of Y .
- (2) If I is an AT-subalgebra of X , then $f(I)$ is an AT-subalgebra of Y .
- (3) If J is an AT-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an AT-ideal of X .
- (4) If J is an AT-subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an AT-subalgebra of X .
- (5) $\text{Ker} f$ is an AT-ideal of X .
- (6) $\text{Im } f$ is an AT-subalgebra of Y .

Proof.

Assume that $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is an AT-homomorphism.

- (1) Let I be an AT-ideal of X . We see that $0 \in I$, and by theorem (4.3(1)), $0' = f(0) \in f(I)$, so $0' \in f(I)$. Now, assume that $f(x) * (f(y) * f(z)) \in f(I)$ and $f(y) \in f(I)$, it follows that $f(x * z) \in f(I)$, so $x * (y * z) \in I$. Since I is an AT-ideal of $x, y, z \in I$, it follows that $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an AT-ideal of Y .

- (2) Let I be an AT-subalgebra of X and $x, y \in f(I)$. Then there exist $a, b \in I$ such that $x = f(a)$ and $y = f(b)$. Since $x * y = f(a) * f(b) = f(a * b) \in f(I)$. Thus $f(I)$ is an AT-subalgebra of Y .

- (3) Let J be an AT-ideal in Y . Then $0' \in J$, we get that $0 = f^{-1}(0') \in f^{-1}(J)$. For any $x, y, z \in X$, let $x * (y * z) \in f^{-1}(J)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(J)$. It follows that $f(x) * (f(y) * f(z)) = f(x * (y * z)) \in J$ and $f(y) \in J$. Since J is an AT-

ideal of Y , we obtain that $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) \in J$. Consequently $y \in f^{-1}(J)$, proving that $f^{-1}(J)$ is an AT-ideal of X .

(4) Let J be an AT-subalgebra of Y and $x, y \in f^{-1}(J)$. Then $f(x) = a$ and $f(y) = b$ for some $a, b \in J$. Thus $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = a * b \in J$, as J is an AT-subalgebra. Hence $x * y \in f^{-1}(J)$.

(5) It is clear that $\text{Ker } f \subseteq X$. Since $f(0) = 0'$, so $0 \in \text{Ker } f$. It follows that $\text{Ker } f \neq \emptyset$. Let $x * (y * z) \in \text{Ker } f$ and $y \in \text{Ker } f$. Then $f(x * (y * z)) = 0'$, $f(y) = 0'$. Since $0' = f(x * (y * z)) = f(x) * f(y * z) = f(x) * (f(y) * f(z)) = f(y) * (f(x) * f(z))$, but $f(y) = 0'$, then $(f(x) * f(z)) = 0'$ imply $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) = 0'$ i.e., $x * z \in \text{Ker } f$. Therefore $\text{Ker } f$ is an AT-ideal of X .

(6) Let $a, b \in \text{Im}(f)$, then there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $a = f(x)$ and $b = f(y)$, so $a * b = f(x) * f(y) = f(x * y) \in \text{Im}(f)$. This proves that $\text{Im}(f)$ is an AT-subalgebra of Y . In general, $\text{Im}(f)$ may not be an AT-ideal. \triangle

Example 4.5. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Define an operation $(*)$ on X by :

*	0	1	2
0	0	1	2
1	0	0	0
2	0	0	0

Then, it can be easily show that $(X, *, 0)$ is an AT-algebras. Now, let f be the mapping from X to itself such that $f(0) = 0, f(1) = 0$ and $f(2) = 2$, then we see that $\text{Im}(f) = \{0, 2\}$. So $\text{Im}(f)$ is not an AT-ideal of X , since $2 \in \text{Im}(f)$ and $2 * 1 = 0 \in \text{Im}(f)$, but $1 \notin \text{Im}(f)$.

The next proposition holds, whose verification is routine and omitted.

Remark 4.6. Let f be an AT-homomorphism from an AT-algebra X to an AT-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) f is an epimorphism if and only if $\text{Im}(f) = Y$.
- (2) f is an isomorphism if and only if f^{-1} is an isomorphism.

Theorem 4.7. Let I be an AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X . Defined the map $f: X \rightarrow X/I$ by: $f(x) = [x]_I$, for all $x \in X$. Then f is epimorphism, we call f is **the natural AT-homomorphism of X onto X/I** . Furthermore, $\text{Ker } f = I$.

Proof.

Let I be an AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X and $x, y \in X$. Since $f(x * y) = [x * y]_I = [x]_I \circ [y]_I = f(x) \circ f(y)$, proving that f is an AT-homomorphism.

Next we will show f is surjective, let $[x]_I \in X/I$ and $x \in X$. Then $f(x) = [x]_I$, so f is surjective.

Finally, to show that $\text{Ker } f = I$, let $x \in \text{Ker } f$. We get that $[x]_I = f(x) = [0]_I$, then $x \sim 0$. It follows that $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$. By hypothesis $0 \in I$.

Hence, $x \in I$, this mean $\text{Ker } f \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq \text{Ker } f$, let $x \in I$. Since I is an AT-subalgebra of X , we have $0 \in I$. Thus $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$. It follows that $x \sim 0$, so $[x]_I = [0]_I$. Since $f(x) = [x]_I = [0]_I$, then $x \in \text{Ker } f$. Accordingly, $\text{Ker } f = I$. \triangle

5. Fuzzy AT-ideals of AT-algebras

In this section, we introduce the concept of fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X and we give examples and results of it .

Definition 5.1.[12] Let X be a nonempty set , a **fuzzy subset** μ of X is $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Definition 5.2. Let X be an AT-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of AT-algebra X is called a **fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X** if it satisfies : $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 5.3. Let X be an AT-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of AT-algebra X is called a **fuzzy AT-ideal of X** if it satisfies :

$$\text{FAT}_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \quad ;$$

$$\text{FAT}_2) \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X.$$

Example 5.4. Consider $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with $*$ defined by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	3
2	0	1	0	1	4
3	0	0	0	0	3
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X ; * , 0)$ is an AT-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\mu(0) = t_0, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1$ and $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = t_2$, where $t_0, t_1, t_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $t_0 > t_1 > t_2$.

Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X .

Lemma 5.5. Let μ be a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. Assume that $x \leq y$, then $y * x = 0$, this together with $0 * x = x$ and $\mu(0) \geq \mu(y)$, we get $\mu(0 * x) = \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(0 * (y * x)), \mu(y)\}$
 $= \min\{\mu(0 * 0), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y) \cdot \square$

Theorem 5.6. Let A be a nonempty subset of an AT-algebra X and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal in X if and only if, A is an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Assume that μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0) = 1$, and so $0 \in A$. Let $x * (y * z) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$, and $\mu(x * z) = 1$. This mean that $\mu(x * z) \in A$ i.e; A is an AT-ideal of X .

Conversely suppose A is an AT-ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0) = 1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$, if $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.. If $x * y \notin A$, and $y \in A$, then $(x * (y * z)) \notin A$ (since A is an AT-ideal). Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . \square

Definition 5.7 ([10]). Let X be a nonempty set and μ be a fuzzy subset of X , for $t \in [0,1]$, the set $\mu_t = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a level subset of μ .

Theorem 5.8. Let μ be a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Assume that μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X , by (FAT₁), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x^*(y^*z) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x^*(y^*z)) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x^*z) \geq \min\{\mu(x^*(y^*z)), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x^*z \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an AT-ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (FAT₁) and (FAT₂) are true. If (FAT₁) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is an AT-ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (FAT₂) is not true, then there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\}$.

Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\})/2$, then $\mu(x' * z') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * (y' * z')) > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that

$(x' * (y' * z')) \in \mu_{t'}$ and $(y') \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an AT-ideal, it follows that

$(x' * z') \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x' * z') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction.

Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Corollary 5.9. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of AT-algebra X . If μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is an AT-ideal of X when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Theorem 5.10. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of AT-algebra X . If μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Assume that μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X , let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$. Since μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra, it follows that $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \} \geq t$ and that $(x * y) \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an AT-subalgebra of X .

Conversely, assume $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}$ is not true, then there exist x' and $y' \in X$ such that $\mu(x' * y') < \min \{ \mu(x'), \mu(y') \}$.

Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * y') + \min \{ \mu(x'), \mu(y') \}) / 2$, then

$\mu(x') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min \{ \mu(x'), \mu(y') \} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x') > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$, since $\mu_{t'}$ is an

AT-subalgebra, it follows that $x' * y' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x' * y') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X . \triangle

Proposition 5.11. Every fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Since μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , then by theorem (5.8), for every $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-ideal of X . By proposition (2.15), for every $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is either empty or an AT-subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of AT-algebra X by theorem (5.10). \triangle

Theorem 5.12. Let A be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . Then for any fixed number (t) in an open interval $(0, 1)$, there exists a fuzzy AT-ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof.

Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by
$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$
. Where (t) is a fixed

number in $(0, 1)$. Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$. If $(x^*(y*z)) \notin A$, then $\mu(x^*(y*z)) = 0$ and so

$$\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min \{ \mu(x^*(y*z)), \mu(y) \}.$$

If $(x^*(y*z)) \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x * z) \geq \min \{ \mu(x^*(y*z)), \mu(y) \}$.

If $(x * z) \notin A$, $(x^*(y*z)) \in A$, then $(y) \notin A$, since A is an AT-ideal.

Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*(y*z)), \mu(y)\}$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. \triangle

Theorem 5.13. Let A be a nonempty subset of an AT-algebra X and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X if and only if, A is an AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

Assume that μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x*(y*z)) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x*(y*z)), \mu(y)\} = 1$, and $\mu(x * z) = 1$.

This mean that $(x * z) \in A$, i.e., A is an AT-ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is an AT-ideal of X , since $0 \in A$, $\mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$,

If $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x*(y*z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $(x * z) \notin A$, and $y \in A$, then $(x*(y*z)) \notin A$ (since A is an AT-ideal).

Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*(y*z)), \mu(y)\}$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Theorem 5.14. Let μ be a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X and let μ_{t_1}, μ_{t_2} be two level AT-ideals of μ , where $t_1 < t_2$, then the following are equivalent.

E1) $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$.

E2) There is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Proof.

Assume that $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$. for $t_1 < t_2$ and that there exist $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. Then μ_{t_2} is proper subset of μ_{t_1} , a contradiction.

Conversely suppose that there is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. It follows from $t_1 < t_2$, that $\mu_{t_1} \subset \mu_{t_2}$. Let $x \in \mu_{t_1}$. Then $\mu(x) \geq t_1$, and hence $\mu(x) \geq t_2$, because $\mu(x)$ does not lie between t_1 and t_2 .

Hence $x \in \mu_{t_2}$, this implies that $\mu_{t_1} \subset \mu_{t_2}$. Therefore, $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$. \triangle

Proposition 5.15. The intersection of any set of fuzzy AT-ideals of AT-algebra X is also fuzzy AT-ideal .

Proof.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy AT-ideals of AT- algebra X , then for any $x, y, z \in X, i \in \Lambda,$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \inf(\mu_i(0)) \geq \inf(\mu_i(x)) = (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \text{ and}$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * z) = \inf(\mu_i(x * z)) \geq \inf(\min\{\mu_i(x*(y*z)), \mu_i(y)\})$$

$$= \min\{\inf(\mu_i(x*(y*z)), \inf(\mu_i(y))\}$$

$$= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x*(y*z)), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\} . \text{ This completes the proof. } \triangle$$

6. Homomorphism of fuzzy AT-ideals

In this section, first we introduce the concept AT-homomorphism of fuzzy AT- ideal of AT-algebra X , also we give examples and results of it .

Now, we shall introduce the concept of a fuzzy Kernel of a function and some properties of it and we shall introduce the concept of a normal fuzzy of a function and some properties of it.

Definition 6.1. Let X and Y be two AT-algebras and $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be a homomorphism. We define **the fuzzy Kernel of f**, $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by :

$$\text{ker } f_{zz} f(x) = \begin{cases} X(0) & x \in \text{ker } f \\ 0 & x \notin \text{ker } f \end{cases}$$

Proposition 6.2. $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X .

Proof. Since $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(0) = X(0)$, then $\text{Kerf}_{zzf} \neq \emptyset$, let $x, y, z \in X$, then

1. If $x * z \in \text{Kerf}$, hence

$$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x * z) = X(0) \geq \min\{\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x*(y*z)), \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(y)\}.$$

2. If $x * z \notin \text{Kerf}$, then $(x*(y*z)) \notin \text{Ker } f, y \notin \text{Ker } f$

$$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x*(y*z)), \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(y)\}.$$

3. If $x \notin \text{Kerf}$, then $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x) = 0 \leq X(x)$ and

If $x \in \text{Kerf}$, then $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x) = X(0) = X(x)$.

$x * z \notin \text{Kerf}$, hence $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x * z) = 0$

$$= \min\{\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(x*(y*z)), \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(y)\}.$$

Therefore $\text{Kerf}_{zz}f(x * z) \geq \min \{ \text{Kerf}_{zz}f(x*(y*z)), \text{Kerf}_{zz}f(y) \}$.

Hence, $\text{Kerf}_{zz}f$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . \triangle

Definition 6.3. Let f be a mapping from the set $(X; *, 0)$ to a set $(Y; *, 0')$. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset B of Y defined by :

$$f(\mu)(y) = B(y) =$$

$$\begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X, f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is called **the image of μ under f** .

Similarly, if B is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = B(f(x))$, for all $x \in X$, is called **the preimage of B under f** .

Theorem 6.4. Let X and Y be two AT-algebras and $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then :

- 1) If S is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X , then $f(S)$ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of Y .
- 2) If I is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y .
- 3) If G is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(G)$ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X .
- 4) If J is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

1) Let S be a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{ \mu(a), \mu(b) \}$, for all $a, b \in S$ and let $x, y \in f(S)$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in S$. Then $\mu(x *' y) =$

$\mu(f(a) *' f(b)) = \mu(f(a * b)) \geq \min \{ \mu(f(a)), \mu(f(b)) \} = \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}$. Hence $f(S)$ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of Y .

2) Let I be a fuzzy AT-ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and $\mu(x * z) \geq \min \{ \mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y) \}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y, z \in f(I)$

that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, $z = f(c)$, for some $a, b, c \in I$, then

$\mu(x *' z) = \mu(f(a) *' f(c)) = \mu(f(a * c)) \geq \min \{ \mu(f(a * (b * c))), \mu(f(b)) \}$
 $= \min \{ \mu(f(a) *' (f(b) *' f(c))), \mu(f(b)) \} = \min \{ \mu(x *' (y *' z)), \mu(y) \}$, for all $x, y, z \in Y$. Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y .

3) Let G be a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of Y , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{ \mu(a), \mu(b) \}$,

for all $a, b \in G$ and let $x, y \in f^{-1}(G)$ that means $x = f^{-1}(a)$, $y = f^{-1}(b)$, for some $a, b \in G$, since $x, y \in f^{-1}(G)$ that means $a = f(x)$, $b = f(y)$, for some $a, b \in G$. Then $\mu(x * y) =$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu(f^{-1}(a) * f^{-1}(b)) = \mu(f^{-1}(a * b)) \geq \min \{ \mu(f^{-1}(a)), \mu(f^{-1}(b)) \} \\ & = \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(G)$ is a fuzzy AT-subalgebra of X .

4) Let J be a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and $\mu(f(x) * f(z)) \geq \min \{ \mu(f(x) * (f(y) * f(z))), \mu(f(y)) \}$, for all $x, y, z \in Y$.

Clearly, $0' \in f(J)$ and let $a, b, c \in f^{-1}(J)$ that means $a = f^{-1}(x)$, $b = f^{-1}(y)$, $c = f^{-1}(z)$, for some $x, y, z \in J$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(a * c) &= \mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(z)) = \mu(f^{-1}(x * z)) \\ &\geq \min \{ \mu(f^{-1}(x * (y * z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y)) \} \\ &= \min \{ \mu(f^{-1}(x) * (f^{-1}(y) * f^{-1}(z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y)) \} \\ &= \min \{ \mu(a * (b * c)), \mu(b) \}, \text{ for all } a, b, c \in X. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(J)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . Δ

Theorem 6.5. An onto homomorphism preimage of a fuzzy AT-ideal is also fuzzy AT-ideal.

Proof.

Let J be a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y and μ the preimage of J under f . Then $J(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, (FAT₁) hold, since $\mu(0) = J(f(0)) \geq J(f(x)) = \mu(x)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x, y, z \in X, \text{ then } \mu(x * z) &= J(f(x * z)) = J(f(x) * f(z)) \\ &\geq \min \{ J(f(x) * (f(y) * f(z))), J(f(y)) \} = \min \{ J(f(x * (y * z))), J(f(y)) \} \\ &= \min \{ \mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mu(x) = J(f(x))$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . Δ

Now, we describe congruence on normal AT-ideal as [11].

Definition 6.6. A fuzzy AT-ideal A of an AT-algebra X is called **normal** if $A(x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 6.7. Let A be a fuzzy AT-ideal of an AT-algebra X . If A is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal, $A(0) \geq t$, then A_t is a normal AT-ideal of X_t .

Definition 6.8. $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X .

Proposition 6.9. Let A be a fuzzy AT-ideal of an AT-algebra X . If A is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal, then A_t is a normal AT-ideal of X_t , for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$.

Proposition 6.10. $\text{Kerf}_{zzf}: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

By proposition (6.2) Kerf_{zzf} is fuzzy AT-ideal of X . We must prove that Kerf_{zzf} is normal (i.e. let $a, b \in X$,

$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) \geq \min \{ \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$).

1. If $a \in \text{Kerf}$, then $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \text{Kerf}$ and

$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = X(0) \geq \min \{ \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$

2. If $a \notin \text{Kerf}$, then either $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \text{Kerf}$ or $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \notin \text{Kerf}$
 $a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \in \text{Kerf}$ implies that

$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = X(0) \geq \min \{ \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$

$a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a \notin \text{Kerf}$ implies that

$\text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = 0 = \min \{ \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(b), X(a) \}$

Hence Kerf_{zzf} is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X . \triangle

Proposition 6.11. Let A be fuzzy AT-ideal of an AT-algebra X , B be a fuzzy AT-ideal of an AT-algebra Y . $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be an epimorphism, then :

1. $f(A)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y .

2. $f^{-1}(B)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X .

Proof.

(1) Let $x, y, z \in Y$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y, c = f^{-1}(z)$ where $a, b, c \in X$,
 $f(A)(x * z) = \sup \{ \min \{ A(a*(b*c)), A(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), c = f^{-1}(z) \}$.

$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ X(a*(b*c)), A(b) \} \mid a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), c = f^{-1}(z) \}$.

$= \sup \{ \min \{ Y(x*(y*z)), f(A)(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b), z = f(c) \}$.

$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ f(A)(x*(y*z)), f(A)(y) \} \mid x = f(a), y = f(b), z = f(c) \}, [11]$.

$\geq \min \{ f(A)(x*(y*z)), f(A)(y) \}$.

Because A is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , for any $x \in X$, we have $A(0) = 1 \geq A(x)$, so $f(A)(0) = \max \{ A(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(0) \} = A(0) = 1$.

Hence $f(A)$ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y .

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{(2) Let } a, b, c \in X \text{ such that } f^{-1}(x) = a, f^{-1}(y) = b, f^{-1}(z) = c \text{ where } x, y \in Y \\
 & f^1(B)(a * c) = \sup \{ \min \{ B(x*(y*z)), B(y) \} \mid x=f(a), y=f(b), z=f(c) \}. \\
 & \geq \sup \{ \min \{ Y(x*(y*z)), B(y) \} \mid x=f(a), y=f(b), z=f(c) \}. \\
 & = \sup \{ \min \{ X(a*(b*c)), f^1(B)(b) \} \mid a=f^1(x), b=f^1(y), c=f^1(z) \}. \\
 & \geq \sup \{ \min \{ f^1(B)(a*(b*c)), f^1(B)(b) \} \mid a=f^1(x), b=f^1(y), c=f^1(z) \}. \text{by [11]}. \\
 & \geq \min \{ f^1(B)(a*(b*c)), f^1(B)(b) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Because B is a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra Y, , for any y ∈ Y, we have B(0') = 1 ≥ B(y), so f^1(B)(0') = max {B(y) | y ∈ f(0)} = B(0') = 1.

Hence f^1(B) is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X. Δ

Proposition 6.12. Let X and Y be two AT-algebras and f: (X; *, 0) → (Y; *, 0') be a homomorphism, and A : R → [0,1] is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X and B : R' → [0,1] is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y, then:

1. f(A) is normal fuzzy AT-ideal of Y, if A is normal and f is surjective.
2. f^1(B) is normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X, if B is normal.

Proof.

(1) f(A) is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y by proposition (6.11). Now, we must prove that f(A) is normal. Let x, y ∈ R' such that f(a) = x, f(b) = y, where a, b ∈ R.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(A)(x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x) &= f(A)(f(a^{-1}) \cdot f(b) \cdot f(a)) = f[A(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a)] \\
 &\geq f[\min \{ A(b), X(a) \}] \\
 &= \sup \{ \min \{ \min \{ A(b), X(a) \} \mid a=f^1(x), b=f^1(y) \} \}. \\
 &\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ A(b), X(a) \} \mid a=f^1(x), b=f^1(y) \} \}. \\
 &\geq \min \{ f(A)(y), Y(x) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence f(A) is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of Y.

(2) f^1(B) is a fuzzy AT-ideal of Y by proposition (6.11).

To prove f^1(B) is normal. Let a, b ∈ R such that f(a) = x, f(b) = y, where x, y ∈ R'. f^1(B)(a^{-1} \cdot b \cdot a) = f^1(B)(f^{-1}(x^{-1}) \cdot f^{-1}(y) \cdot f^{-1}(x))

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= f^1(B)(x^{-1} \cdot y \cdot x). \\
 &\geq f[\min \{ B(y), Y(x) \}]. \\
 &= \sup \{ \min \{ \min \{ B(y), Y(x) \} \mid x=f(a), y=f(b) \} \}. \\
 &\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ B(y), Y(x) \} \mid f(a) = x, f(b) = y \} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\geq \min \{ f^{-1}(B) (b), X(a) \}.$$

Hence $f^{-1}(B)$ is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X . \triangle

FUNDAMENTAL THEOREMS

Now, we shall introduce the fundamental theorems of fuzzy AT-algebras.

Theorem 6.13 : (First Fuzzy Isomorphism Theorem)

Let X and Y be two AT-algebras and $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be a homomorphism. Then $X / \text{Kerf}_{zzf} \approx f(X)$.

Proof.

Define $g: X/\text{Kerf} \rightarrow f(X)$ such that: $g(a + \text{Kerf}) = f(a)$, for each $a + \text{Kerf} \in X / \text{Kerf}$. By definition, g is a nonempty function of X / Kerf since $g(0 + \text{Kerf}) = f(0)$

Let $a + \text{Kerf}, b + \text{Kerf} \in X / \text{Kerf}$, $a + \text{Kerf} = b + \text{Kerf}$ implies that $a * b \in \text{Kerf}$, therefore $f(a * b) = 0'$ and f is homomorphism, then $f(a) * f(b) = 0'$ implies $f(a) = f(b)$. Thus $g(a + \text{Kerf}) = g(b + \text{Kerf})$. Hence g is well – define.

Now, we must prove g is an isomorphism

First, if $g(a + \text{Kerf}) = g(b + \text{Kerf})$, then $f(a) = f(b)$ and $f(a) * f(b) = 0'$ implies that $f(a * b) = 0'$. Thus $a * b \in \text{Kerf}$ therefore $a + \text{Kerf} = b + \text{Kerf}$, g is one-to-one.

Second, for any $b \in f(X)$ there exists $a \in X$ such that: $f(a) = b$ since f is onto then $f(a) = g(a + \text{Kerf}) = b$, g is onto.

Finally, Let $a + \text{Kerf}, b + \text{Kerf} \in X / \text{Kerf}$

$$g[(a + \text{Kerf}) \oplus (b + \text{Kerf})] = g[(a + b) + \text{Kerf}] = f(a + b) = f(a) + f(b) = g(a + \text{Kerf}) + g(b + \text{Kerf})$$

$$g[(a + \text{Kerf}) \otimes (b + \text{Kerf})] = g[(a \cdot b) + \text{Kerf}] = f(a \cdot b) = f(a) \cdot f(b) = g(a + \text{Kerf}) \cdot g(b + \text{Kerf})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Moreover, } X / \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a + \text{Kerf}) &= \sup \{ X / \text{Kerf}_{zzf}(a + \text{Kerf}) \mid a + \text{Kerf} \in \text{Kerf}_{zzf} \} = X(a) \\ &= f(X)(f(a)) \text{ where } f(X)(a + \text{Kerf}) = \sup \{ X(b) \mid b \in f^{-1}(f(a)) \} \\ &= Y(f^{-1}(a)) = X(a). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $X/\text{Kerf}_{zzf} \approx f(X)$. \triangle

Proposition 6.14. Let I be an AT-ideal of AT-algebra X , A be a fuzzy AT-ideal of AT-algebra X . Then the fuzzy subset B of X/I define by :

$B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}$ is a fuzzy of AT-ideal of the quotient ring in X/I .

Proof.

Define $B: X/I \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}$ since $B(0+I) = A(0)$, B is nonempty fuzzy subset of X/I . Let $a+I, b+I, c+I \in X/I, a + I = b + I$, then $b = a + d$, for some $d \in I$.

$$B(a + I) = \sup \{ A(b + x) \mid x \in I \} = \sup \{ A(a + d + x) \mid x \in I \} \\ = \sup \{ A(a + y) \mid y = x + d \in I \} = B(b + I).$$

Hence B is a well – defined.

Now, we must prove B is a fuzzy AT-ideal of X / I .

$$1. \quad B[(a + I) * (c + I)] = B[(a * c) + I] = \sup \{ A((a * c) + x) \mid x \in I \} \\ \geq \sup \{ \min \{ A(((a * (b * c)) + x) \mid x \in I \}, \min \{ A(b + x) \mid x \in I \} \} \\ = \sup \{ \min \{ A(a * (b * c)) + (v * (w * u)) \mid x = v * (w * u) \in I \}, \min \{ A(b + w) \mid w \in I \} \} \\ = \sup \{ \min \{ A((a + v) * [(b + w) * (c + w)]) \mid w, v, u \in I \}, \min \{ A(b + w) \mid w \in I \} \} \\ \geq \min \{ \sup \{ A((a + v) * [(b + w) * (c + w)]) \mid v * (w * u) \in I \}, \sup \{ A(b + w) \mid w \in I \} \} \\ = \min \{ B((a * (b * c)) + I), B(b + I) \} \\ = \min \{ B([(a + I) * (b + I)] * (c + I)), B[b + I] \}.$$

Then $B[(a + I) * (c + I)] \geq \min \{ B([(a + I) * (b + I)] * (c + I)), B[b + I] \}$.

$$2. \quad B(0 + I) = \sup \{ A(a + x) \mid x \in I \}, 0 \in X. = A(0) = 1. \text{ Then } B(0 + I) = A(0) = 1. \\ \text{Hence } B \text{ is a fuzzy AT-ideal of } X / I. \triangle$$

Proposition 6.15. Let X be an AT-algebra and A be a fuzzy AT-ideal of X . Let I be an AT-ideal of X maximal among those contained in $A * \cap X^*$. Then there exists a bijection between the fuzzy AT-ideals of X / A and the fuzzy AT-ideals A of X such that $I \subseteq A^*$, (where the set $A^* = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0) \}$).

Proof. Let $B = \{ A' \mid A' \text{ fuzzy AT-ideal of } X, I \subseteq A^* \}$, $C = \{ A'' \mid A'' \text{ fuzzy AT-ideal of } X / A \}$. $f : X \rightarrow X / I$ such that $f(a) = a + I, a \in X$. Note that f is a homomorphism by proposition (6.14).

Let $h : B \rightarrow C$ such that $h(A') = f(A')$, $h(A')(a) = a + I$. $k : C \rightarrow B$ such that $k(A'') = f^{-1}(A'')$, $k(A'')(a + I) = a$.

Now, to prove that $k \circ h = i_B, h \circ k = i_C$. $(k \circ h)(A')(x) = k(h(A')(x))$, $x \in X = f^{-1}(f(A')(x))$.

$$= \sup \{A'(y) \mid y \in f^{-1}(f(x))\} = \sup \{A'(x + z) \mid z \in I\} = A'(x) .$$

Therefore $k \circ h = i_B$.

$$\begin{aligned} (h \circ k)(A'')(y) &= h(k(A'')(y)) \quad , y \in X / I . \\ &= f(f^{-1}(A'')(y)) = \sup \{A''(x + z) \mid z \in I, x \in f^{-1}(y)\} . \\ &= \sup \{A''(y) \mid y \in f(f^{-1}(x))\} = A''(y) . \text{ Hence } h \circ k = i_C . \end{aligned}$$

Now, we must prove that k, h are bijection .

$1 - 1$: $h(x) = h(y)$, then $x + I = y + I$ implies that $x - y \in I$ and $x = y$, h is $1 - 1$.
 $k(x + I) = k(y + I)$, then $x = y$, k is $1 - 1$.

onto : for all $x \in X$, there exists $y \in X$ such that $x = y + z, z \in I$, then $x \in y + I$, hence k is onto.

For all $x \in X$, there exists $y \in X$ such that $y \in x + I$ implies that $z \in I, y = x + z$, hence h is onto .

Then there exists a bijection between the fuzzy AT-algebra of X / A and the fuzzy AT-algebra A of X such that $I \subseteq A^* . \triangle$

Remark 6.16.

1. If f and g are isomorphism, then $g \circ f$ is an isomorphism since f and g are $1 - 1$ and onto implies that $g \circ f$ is $1 - 1$ and onto.
2. If f and g are homomorphism , $1 - 1$ and onto, then $g \circ f$ is an isomorphism .

Theorem 6.17 : (Second Fuzzy Isomorphism Theorem)

Let X and Y be two AT-algebras and $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, let A and B be fuzzy AT-ideals of an AT-algebra X , with $A \subseteq B$ such that $A^* = B^*$ (i.e. $B(x) = B(0)$, whenever $A(x) = A(0)$). Then $(X / A) / (B / A) \approx (X / B)$.

Proof.

B / A is a normal fuzzy AT-ideal of X / A by proposition (6.15), by proposition (6.12) .

Let $B / A(x + I_1) = B(x)$ where I_1 is the normal AT-ideal of X maximal among those contained in $A^* \cap X^*$, because

$B / A(x + I_1) = \max \{B(y) \mid y + I_1 = x + I_1\}$ and since $y^{-1} \cdot x \in A^*$, we have $y^{-1} \cdot x \in B^*$ and therefore $B(y) = B(x)$.

$(X / A)^* = X / I_1$ and $(B / A)^* = B^* / I_1$.

So, the normal AT-ideal of X / I_1 maximal among those contained in

$(X/A)^* \cap (B/A)^*$ may be written as I_2 / I_1 , where I_2 is the normal AT-ideal of X maximal among those contained in $X^* \cap B^*$.

It is well known that $f: (X / I_1) / (I_2 / I_1) \rightarrow X / I_2$ such that : $f(x + I_1 + (I_2 / I_1)) = x + I_2$ is an isomorphism by remark (6.16) .

Moreover, $(X / A) / (B / A) (x + I_1 + (I_2 / I_1)) = X / A (x + I_1) = X(x) = X / B (x + I_2)$. Hence $(X / A) / (B / A) \approx (X / B)$. \triangle

References

- [1] Asawasamrit S. and Sudprasert A. , **A Structure of KK-Algebras and its Properties** , Int. Journal of Math. Analysis, vol. 6, no. 21 (2012),1035-1044.
- [2] Asawasamrit S., **KK-Isomorphism and its Properties** , Int. Journal of Pure and Applied Math., vol. 78, no. 1 (2012), 65-73.
- [3] Bhattacharya P. and Mukherjee N. P., **Fuzzy relations and fuzzy group**, Inform. Sci. , vol.36 (1985), 267-282.
- [4] Hameed A.T., **Fuzzy ideal of some algebras** ,PH.D.SC. Thesis, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Egypt ,(2015).
- [5] Hameed A.T., Mostafa S.M. and Abed A.H., **Big Generalized Fuzzy KUS-ideals of KUS-algebra**, College of Education Journal in AL-Mustansiryah University 26-27 April 2017.
- [6] Hameed A.T., Mostafa S.M. and Abed A.H., **Cubic KUS-ideals of KUS-algebras**, Asian Journal of Mathematical Sciences, vol.8, no.2, pp:36 - 43, (2017).
- [7] Hu Q. P. and Li X., **Proper BCH-algebras**, Math. Japonica , vol.30 (1985), 659-661.
- [8] Hu Q. P. and Li X. , **On BCH-algebras**, Math. Seminar Notes , vol.11(1983), 313-320.
- [9] Iseki K. and Yanaka S., **An introduction to theory of BCK-algebras**, Math. Japonica , vol. 23 (1979), 1-20.
- [10] Iseki K.,**On BCI-algebras**, Math. Seminar Notes ,vol. 8 (1980), 125-130.
- [11] Mostafa S. M., **Fuzzy implicative ideals in BCK - algebras**, fuzzy sets and systems ,vol. 87 (1997) , 361-368 .

- [12] Mostafa S. M, Abdel Naby M.A., Abdel-Halim F. and Hameed A.T., **On KUS-algebras**, International Journal of Algebra, vol.7, no.3, pp: 131-144 , (2013).
- [13] Mostafa S.M., Abdel Naby M.A. and Hameed A.T., **Fuzzy ideals of Dual QS-algebras**, JCSI International Journal of Computer Science Issues, vol. 10, Issue 2, no 1, March (2013).
- [14] Mostafa S.M., Abdel Naby M.A. and Hameed A.T., **KUS-algebra is equivalent to dual QS-algebra**, GBS Publishers & Distributors (India), vol.1, no.1, pp: 109-114, (2013).
- [15] Mostafa S.M., Abdel Naby M.A., Abdel-Halim F. and Hameed A.T., **Interval-valued fuzzy KUS-ideal**, IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM), vol.5, Issue 4, pp: 61-66, (2013).
- [16] Mostafa S.M., Hameed A.T. and Abed A.H., **Fuzzy KUS-ideals of KUS-algebra**, Basra Journal of Science (A), 34, 2 (2016), 73-84. Mostafa S.M., Hameed A.T. and Mohammed N.Z., **Fuzzy α -Translation of KUS-algebras**, Journal Al-Qadisyah for Computer Science and Mathematics, 8, 2 (2016), 8-16.
- [17] Mostafa S.M., Hameed A.T. and Alfatlawi_A.A., **KUS-algebras defined by Fuzzy Points**, Global Journal of Mathematics, vol.8, no.1, pp:802-810, (2016).
- [18] Mostafa S.M., Hameed A.T., **Anti-fuzzy KUS-ideals of KUS-algebra**, International Journal of Computer Applications, vol.70, no.9, pp: 24-28, (2013).
- [19] Mukherjee T.K. and Sen M.K., **On Fuzzy Ideals of a Ring I**, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, vol.21(1987) , pp. 99 – 104.
- [20] Zadeh L.A., **Fuzzy sets** , inform . and control ,vol.8 (1965) , 338-353.